

FROM FAIRY TALES IN TEACHING ENGLISH METHODS OF USE

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Abstract. *The article explains the importance of using fairy tales in teaching English. It also explains the effective use of fairy tales in English lessons and the educational value of fairy tales.*

Keywords: *fairy tale, linguistic competence, English lesson, textbook, students' creative abilities.*

The increasing demand for learning and teaching foreign languages presents the modern teacher with sets the task of using new methods of teaching. Communicative competences formation is the main goal of teaching English. The teacher's task is the student's speech abilities, lexical reserves, grammatical and syntactic aspects of the English language and their future is to form ideas to ensure its development.

Practice shows that fairy tales are an effective source of teaching foreign languages at an early age. They represent the uniqueness of people, their culture, traditions, moral principles, especially their national life and clearly show the way of life. At the same time, English-speaking countries fairy tales along with cultural diversity, universal human values instilled in them from childhood reflects.

Fairy tales develop children's imagination, are a connection between imagination and the real world serves, the student will have some experience of social life. These things are foreign to students causes the development of social and cultural competence of language learning. There are many teachers years of experience in learning fairy tales: attracts children allows us to emphasize that it increases interest. The fairy tale, in turn, affects their emotional state: reduce anxiety and negativity, to feel and connect with your favorite characters provides nourishment, creates an atmosphere of motivation and joy.

Any lesson as a methodological whole system is not only educational, but also developmental and educational also has goals. Therefore, the English lesson is not only about

enriching the vocabulary, reading texts and should not be limited to the ability to translate or understand someone else's speech.

Also, the student learns to critically accept and analyze the information received during the lesson necessary, in addition, the teacher should help to develop the ability to think logically.

It is difficult to develop communicative competence in English without being in the country where the language is being studied.

Therefore, the important task of the teacher is to use various methods (role games, discussions, creative projects, etc.) is to create real and imaginary communication situations in a foreign language lesson.

The task of introducing students to the cultural values of the country where the language is being studied is important. Text and related images play a big role in achieving these goals.

The advantage of modern English language textbooks is undoubtedly their wealth of regional geographical information. In-text ads, icons, profiles, menus and other miscellaneous information takes an important place. All facts about different areas of life in English-speaking countries, information and events are selected taking into account the age and interests of the students. This mastering the material allows students to visit in the future (for reading, travel, business, etc.) will provide an opportunity to better explore the country.

At the same time, students are introduced to the life, customs, and language of English-speaking countries. It is very important to give a visual representation of reality. Fairy tales can serve this purpose, their use is the most important requirement of communicative methodology - the process of language acquisition helps realize understanding as a reality of life.

A possible option for working with a fairy tale can be as follows:

1. Preparatory work. Students are given the name of the fairy tale and they give their guesses about the plot. Then new vocabulary necessary for understanding the fairy tale is introduced. New before reading each chapter dictionaries are included.

2. Perception of a fairy tale (divided into parts). Discuss with students before reading each part will be done.

- Who is the main character? Who is the main character?
- Do we like him? Do we like him?
- What did he do? What did he do?

3. Test your understanding of the main content.

First, students answer the questions given to the teacher before reading. Then From the exercises "Choose the correct answer", "Place the sentences in a logical sequence", etc you can use.

4. Development of oral speech skills.

Communicative speech can be stimulated using various tasks.

- describe the main character;
- performing the dialogue between the characters;
- comment on the character's behavior;
- what phrases do we use to describe the character.

It is known that one of the most important reading skills is the ability to predict, but its it is very important in reading fairy tales. In the process of working with them, students were unfamiliar to themselves they can guess the meaning of the words in the context, which in many ways generalizes their content provides understanding. The main thing is not only to teach students to

read and understand texts, but also It is also very important to instill a love for reading.

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